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ABSTRACT

Decentralized finance (DeFi), which executes financial transactions using blockchain without an intermediary, has attracted over US\$250 billion in total value locked (TVL) at its peak. However, little is known about how DeFi protocols assure users of the safety of their investments. This paper provides the first empirical evidence on DeFi audit services that check and verify the smart contracts underlying these protocols. Using data on 316 of the largest protocols, we find that those vetted by more smart contract auditors and by higher quality auditors have higher TVL and that these protocols have higher market capitalization (native token values). Using an event study approach, we document that TVL and token values significantly increase after a protocol's first audit, especially those involving a high-quality auditor. We also find that protocols with more auditors and higher audit quality exhibit a smaller drop in TVL and token values after the collapse of the TerraUSD stablecoin, which reduced aggregate DeFi TVL by almost 65%. Overall, our findings suggest that DeFi users and investors perceive audits as providing assurance regarding the safety of their deposits and investments.

1. Introduction

Decentralized finance (DeFi) protocols use algorithmically programmed smart contracts that operate autonomously on blockchains to execute transactions. Users interact with these protocols to deposit, borrow, and exchange blockchain-based financial assets, i.e., tokens. Unlike traditional financial transactions, in which users trust intermediaries such as banks or brokerages based on reputation and regulation, DeFi protocols build trust through transparency, e.g., open source code that allows anyone to verify the intent of the smart contract. Harvey et al. (2021) highlight DeFi's potential to replace traditional financial institutions and hail it as the future of finance. At its height in November 2021, DeFi protocols, in aggregate, attracted over US\$250 billion in deposits, while recently, in March 2023, Uniswap, a decentralized exchange, had 40% higher trading volume than Coinbase, one of the most prominent centralized exchanges (Financial Times, 2023).

The open source nature of DeFi is a double-edged sword. On the one hand, making the underlying code of smart contracts publicly

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accessible allows tech-savvy users to examine the codes and ensure the safety of their deposits. On the other hand, this transparency enables rogue entities (e.g., hackers) to identify and exploit vulnerabilities for personal gain. These exploits, also referred to as DeFi or smart contract hacks, pose great risk to DeFi users. For example, blockchain analytics firm Chainalysis estimates that US\$2.2 billion was stolen via smart contract hacks in 2021 (Chainalysis, 2022).

To mitigate this risk and attract users, DeFi protocols can hire an external party to inspect their code, a process commonly referred to as DeFi or smart contract audits. During these audits, smart contract auditors, who are experts in the programming languages commonly used in blockchains and have in-depth knowledge about DeFi, carefully examine protocols' codes and look for vulnerabilities. After an inspection, DeFi auditors usually publish a report detailing their work scope, audit process, and findings, including deficiencies along with protocols' remedial actions. DeFi auditors such as TrailOfBits and Quantstamp claim that their services help safeguard user assets (Quantstamp, 2023; TrailOfBits, 2023). Regulators, central banks, think tanks, and law enforcement groups also recommend DeFi audits to reduce the risk of loss for users (FBI, 2022; OECD, 2022; European Systemic Risk Board, 2023; Fliche et al., 2023; U.S. Treasury, 2023).

Ex ante, DeFi audits can assure users of the safety of the protocol in two respects. First, as DeFi is a nascent field, many protocols are developed and maintained by persons or entities with little track record or reputation on which the users can rely to judge the quality of protocols. Second, most DeFi users lack the relevant expertise to verify the security of DeFi protocols. However, it is also possible that users regard DeFi audits as "cheap talk" that provides no value because these audits have no uniformly accepted standards. Furthermore, DeFi auditors are start-ups not subject to government regulation and with few reputational concerns. They must also convince potential clients that their service is necessary, which can lead to conflicts of interest and competition to lower fees, negatively affecting service quality. Ultimately, whether DeFi audits improve protocol value is an empirical question.

We answer this question using a comprehensive sample of 316 of the largest DeFi protocols. We use users' cryptocurrency deposits or total value locked (hereafter TVL) to measure their confidence in the security of DeFi protocols, and the market capitalization of protocols' native tokens, which are used to facilitate the functions of the smart contract and govern protocols, to measure investors' valuation of the protocols. First, using protocol-level analyses, we find that DeFi protocols with more auditors and those with more prominent and higher quality auditors are associated with a greater amount of user deposits (i.e., higher TVL) and higher native token values. Second, we use two event-study designs to mitigate endogeneity concerns and provide causal evidence that DeFi audits enhance user confidence and protocol value. In the first test, we find that protocols experience a significant increase in user deposits and token values after their first audit, especially if the audit is conducted by a high-quality auditor. In the second test, we document that audited protocols experience a milder drop in TVL and token value after an exogenous shock that lowers the community's confidence, namely the TerraUSD collapse in May 2022; and that this shielding effect is stronger for protocols audited by more auditors or by higher quality auditors. In summary, our findings suggest that DeFi users and investors perceive audits as providing assurance regarding the safety of their deposits and investments.

Our paper contributes to several streams of literature. First, we contribute to the nascent literature on cryptocurrencies and DeFi. Most papers related to DeFi focus on regulatory aspects, stablecoins, or liquidity risks (Aramonte et al., 2021; Chiu et al., 2022; Gudgeon, Werner, et al., 2020; Momtaz, 2022) or provide an overview of this field (Auer et al., 2023; Chohan, 2021; Harvey et al., 2021; Makarov & Schoar, 2022; Werner et al., 2021; Zetzsche et al., 2020). We are the first to provide empirical evidence on how DeFi audits improve user confidence and protocol valuation.

Second, our paper relates to the voluntary audit literature. Prior studies document that voluntary audits following a clear set of guidelines lead to positive outcomes such as improved credit ratings, greater access to credit, and lower cost of capital (Allee & Yohn, 2009; Lennox & Pittman, 2011; Lisowsky & Minnis, 2020; Minnis, 2011). Our results show that voluntary audits by unregulated auditors with far less experience and reputation than traditional CPA firms still provide benefits. We also add to the literature on information technology (IT) audits by providing empirical evidence of the value of code security audits (Ashraf et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2018; Li et al., 2012; Masli et al., 2010; Schoenfeld, 2022).

Last, our findings have implications for DeFi token holders, regulators, and policymakers. Whereas the SEC argues that most tokens are securities (Gensler, 2022), practitioners disagree because they view tokens as governed solely by decentralized protocols. We show that DeFi protocol deposits and their token values are influenced by audits, which are usually commissioned by protocol developers or by majority token holders who are insiders or early investors (Bhambhwani, 2022; Han et al., 2023). Thus, our evidence supports the SEC's claim that DeFi token values are derived from the efforts of others, thereby meeting one of the criteria for determining what a security is (SEC v. W.J. Howey Co., 328 U.S. 293 [1946]).

2. Institutional background

2.1. Decentralized finance and related literature

The number of protocols in the DeFi market and the value of cryptocurrencies deposited in such protocols have grown rapidly in recent years. In 2019, a few protocols (e.g., MakerDAO, Uniswap, and Compound) had an aggregate TVL of US\$500 million. After the "DeFi Summer" of 2020, the market witnessed a surge in the number of protocols and TVL, with aggregate TVL reaching a peak of US\$250 billion in November 2021. However, the DeFi market experienced a sudden drop in TVL, from US\$185 billion on May 11, 2022 to US\$66 billion on June 19, 2022, due to a combination of interest rate hikes by the U.S. Federal Reserve and a loss of confidence in DeFi after the collapse of Terra-LUNA's UST stablecoin in May 2022. As of July 24, 2023, DeFiLlama (<https://defillama.com>) lists 890 protocols with TVL of over US\$1 million and an aggregate TVL of US\$56 billion across all protocols.

DeFi protocols rely on two key technological innovations: blockchain and smart contracts. Blockchains, or the base layer, are

decentralized databases on which smart contracts are distributed and run (Nakamoto, 2008; Narayanan et al., 2016; Yermack, 2017). Smart contracts, or the protocol layer, are computer programs that run on blockchains (Buterin et al., 2014; Chiu & Koeppel, 2019; Cong & He, 2019; Mohanta et al., 2018). Compared with programs deployed on centralized servers, smart contracts are much more difficult to change once deployed, a feature known as “immutability.” Immutability increases trust in DeFi protocols by ensuring that the movement of funds strictly follows the logic of the code. Interacting with smart contracts also ensures censorship resistance, as no user can be denied access to the contracts (Abadi & Brunnermeier, 2018; Sockin & Xiong, 2023).

DeFi protocols can be grouped into five functional categories (Schär, 2021; Harvey et al., 2021; Auer et al., 2023; U.S. Treasury, 2023). The first and most common is the decentralized exchange (DEX) protocol category, which includes Uniswap and Curve. Also known as automated market makers (AMM), DEX protocols allow users to trade cryptocurrencies without relying on an intermediary, e.g., a centralized exchange such as Binance or Coinbase, that uses order books. Instead, DEXs allow users to deposit funds and trade directly using liquidity pools, which are smart contracts that hold multiple tokens, with prices adjusting based on the relative number of tokens in these pools (Lehar & Parlour, 2021).

The second category is the money market protocol (e.g., Aave and Compound), which allows users to deposit cryptocurrencies into their contracts that become part of a pool of funds available for other users to borrow. Borrowers must provide collateral in the form of cryptocurrency and pay interest (Gudgeon, Werner, et al., 2020). Such interest is paid into the pool and distributed among depositors and the protocol’s native token holders.

The third category is stablecoin protocols such as MakerDAO, which issue and manage cryptocurrencies that peg their value to another asset, usually the U.S. dollar. Most stablecoins rely on over-collateralization to maintain their pegged value, although some use algorithms (Brennecke et al., 2022). Fourth, derivative protocols (e.g., Synthetix) allow users to take leveraged positions on cryptocurrency prices using a pool of other users’ deposits that earn fees on derivative trades (Arslanian, 2022).

Last, investment pooling protocols that invest in other DeFi protocols have emerged recently. For example, automated asset management protocols such as Yearn and Convex algorithmically search for the highest yield in other DeFi protocols, and pooled staking protocols such as Lido gather user deposits and stake them to avoid the high costs of solo staking (Potts et al., 2022). These protocols are similar to collectively managed funds (e.g., mutual funds and hedge funds) in traditional finance.

The rise of DeFi has drawn considerable interest from academics. Recent studies such as Zetzsche et al. (2020), Werner et al. (2021), Meyer et al. (2022), Auer et al. (2023), and Makridis et al. (2023) provide in-depth overviews of this nascent DeFi industry. From a finance perspective, Momtaz (2022) and Chiu et al. (2022) examine the efficiency of the DeFi market, and Cumming et al. (2022) study the performance of cryptocurrency funds. Security implications are discussed by Liu and Liu (2019), Wang, Jin, et al. (2021), Oosthoek (2021), Wang, Jin, et al. (2021), and Zhou et al. (2022). Gudgeon, Werner, et al. (2020) discuss the risks of flash loans and collateralized lending. Blockchain tokens are discussed by Cong et al. (2020), Chod and Lyandres (2021), Cong et al. (2021), Gryglewicz et al. (2021), Bakos and Halaburda (2022), Cong et al. (2022), Chod et al. (2022), and Sockin and Xiong (2023), who argue that these tokens can mitigate moral hazard, reduce information asymmetry, and improve project success.

2.2. DeFi protocol risks

Exploits of smart contracts pose great risks to DeFi protocols because they lead to substantial losses for users. It is important to note that most DeFi protocols are non-custodial, meaning that their developers do not have access to user deposits.¹ These funds (primarily ETH and stablecoins) are instead locked into smart contracts.² Moreover, because DeFi protocols generally have no jurisdictional base, it is difficult, if not impossible, for users to recover lost funds after a DeFi protocol exploit. In this section, we briefly describe the most common types of exploits (see Table IA1 for a list of the amounts and number of exploits of our sample protocols by exploit type). For a more detailed description of smart contract vulnerabilities, we refer readers to Li et al. (2020).

2.2.1. Flash loan attacks

Flash loans are taken out and repaid within the same block, similar to overnight repurchase loans, for which the lender (in DeFi, the protocol) receives a fee plus interest. Flash loans can be used to conduct arbitrage transactions, as a user can borrow from a DeFi protocol, conduct their arbitrage trade, and repay the loan within the same block. These flash loans usually occur within the time it takes for a block to propagate (e.g., 12–15 s for Ethereum). An attacker can exploit DeFi protocols by taking out a flash loan, sending it to another address, and quickly withdrawing it before the loan must be repaid. If the smart contracts of a DeFi protocol do not have sufficient logic and token balance checks to ensure that a flash loan cannot be taken out unless certain balance conditions are met, attackers can exploit this shortcoming and drain the protocol’s deposits. Flash loans can also be used to manipulate cryptocurrency markets, such as by changing the number of tokens in an AMM, which affects token prices. In October 2020, the crypto trading platform Harvest suffered a flash loan attack, resulting in losses of US\$27 million (Cao et al., 2021).

¹ Unlike DeFi protocols, centralized cryptoexchanges (CEXs) such as Coinbase, Kraken, and Binance have custody and control over user deposits. While CEXs can also suffer from code deficiencies, they are not based on open source code (Chiu et al., 2022). Furthermore, CEXs can misappropriate user deposits as evidenced by FTX, and are often affected by banking access issues, such as delayed withdrawals or “frozen deposits” (Galati et al., 2023).

² For example, the Aave protocol’s smart contract (available at: <https://etherscan.io/address/0x030bA81f1c18d280636F32af80b9AA0d2Cf0854e>) holds approximately US\$523 million worth of ETH, as of July 24, 2023.

2.2.2. Code logic errors

Code logic errors in DeFi smart contracts are programming mistakes or vulnerabilities that can cause unexpected or unintended behavior in contract execution. For example, Popsicle Finance suffered a US\$20 million exploit due to code logic errors in its smart contracts causing user balances to not update when transferred from one address to another.³ In another example, some users of the Compound protocol were mistakenly rewarded too many governance tokens, diluting the voting rights of these tokens.⁴

2.2.3. Oracle attacks

Applications on blockchains, including DeFi, may use information from outside of the blockchain. Oracles are applications that provide such information (Beniiche, 2020). Many DeFi exploits involve manipulating oracles to provide inaccurate information to smart contracts for personal gain. For example, some DeFi protocols use oracles to retrieve the prices of cryptocurrencies from exchanges. One type of oracle attack involves manipulating a thinly traded market's token price that is referenced by an oracle. For instance, in an attack on the Venus Protocol, hackers leveraged 900,000 XVS tokens to increase the price referenced by Venus's oracle from US\$80 to US\$145, allowing them to drain US\$77 million from the protocol (Chiu et al., 2022; Werner et al., 2021).

2.2.4. Reentrancy attack

Reentrancy is a vulnerability in smart contracts that allows an attacker to repeatedly execute a function before the previous execution has been completed, allowing the transfer of more funds than what is intended. The first DeFi hack was a reentrancy attack in 2015 on the Ethereum DAO, which resulted in the theft of approximately US\$55 million worth of ETH (Liu et al., 2018). Recently, the Hundred Finance protocol was attacked by hackers who borrowed more assets than their deposited collateral by repeatedly executing borrow functions before the protocol could update the debt balance.⁵

2.2.5. Access control and private key compromise

In theory, DeFi protocols should be decentralized, that is, without centralized points of control (Aramonte et al., 2021). However, some protocols' smart contracts give developers or other supposedly trustworthy individuals greater power than other users, including control of wallets storing users' funds (U.S. Treasury 2023). These protocols usually justify such access for "emergency" reasons in case the protocol fails. To increase security, these wallets often use a multi-signature setup, requiring control of more than one set of private keys to access the wallet (Han et al., 2021). However, multi-signature wallets are not foolproof (Schär, 2021). For example, in December 2021, hackers accessed the private keys BadgerDAO developers' wallet addresses, where users' funds were stored, allowing them to drain approximately US\$120 million (Xu & Feng, 2022).

Furthermore, many developers of DeFi protocols are known only by their aliases, creating the risk that rogue developers may never be caught for exploiting the protocol. Indeed, several instances of "rug-pulls," in which developers create protocols, attract users and deposits, and subsequently steal these deposits, have occurred (Wronka, 2023). Some of these developers replicate prominent open source protocols, also known as a "fork," add backdoor access to the forked code, and refer users to audits of the original protocol to gain trust. For example, in the Compounder Finance scam, rogue developers created a fork of the Compound protocol and drained over US\$11 million in user funds (Scharfman, 2023).

2.3. Auditing DeFi protocols

An audit of DeFi protocols involves a thorough review of the smart contracts that execute transactions. For a smart contract that "locks" cryptocurrencies and allows users to withdraw them, the audit checks not only whether the code performs as intended but also for the above-mentioned vulnerabilities. DeFi auditors often claim that their services help safeguard user assets (Quantstamp, 2023; TrailOfBits, 2023). Government agencies also recommend DeFi audits to reduce the risk of loss for users (FBI, 2022; OECD, 2022; European Systemic Risk Board, 2023; U.S. Treasury, 2023). For instance, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) suggests that DeFi investors "ensure the DeFi investment platform has conducted one or more code audits performed by independent auditors" (FBI, 2022). In this section, we briefly review the audit procedures. For a comprehensive overview of smart contract audits, see Popchev et al. (2022).

2.3.1. Smart contract audit tools

Smart contract auditors use both manual reviews and automated tools to scan for vulnerabilities (He et al., 2020; Liu & Liu, 2019; Wang, Jin, et al., 2021). Manual reviews allow auditors to understand the logic of the code and identify flaws, and automated tools follow pre-determined routines and parse through smart contracts to check for common vulnerabilities. These tools rely on a variety of methods, such as formal verification and input validation (Almakhour et al., 2020; Wang, Jin, et al., 2021). See Liu et al. (2018), Tikhomirov et al. (2018), and Kushwaha et al. (2022) for in-depth discussions of smart contract audit tools.

One such tool is called a "fuzzer" (Jiang et al., 2018). A general interaction between a benign user and a smart contract involves the user sending inputs in line with what the smart contract is expected to accept. In fuzzing, a smart contract auditor, posing as a malicious user, sends malformed inputs to test for vulnerabilities. Popular tools used for this purpose include Echidna (developed by

³ See <https://rekt.news/popsicle-rekt/> for further details.

⁴ See <https://defiyield.app/rekt-database/compound> for further details.

⁵ See <https://rekt.news/agave-hundred-rekt/> for an explanation of the Hundred Finance hack.

TrailOfBits), Mythril (used by ConsenSys), Slither, and Manticore (used by TrailOfBits). Echidna, for example, has been used to audit MakerDAO and Aave (Grieco et al., 2020). Another vulnerability occurs when a contract executes an external call to another contract (e.g., to determine token values, perform calculations, or update user balances) without properly checking the return values. Auditors can use input validation to ensure that all of the inputs returned are appropriate.

There are two points related to smart contract audits and private key compromises that are worth noting. First, most smart contract audits focus on the open source codes of the protocol and do not examine how the developers store their private keys. Second, some of the “hacks” related to private key compromises may be perpetuated by the developers themselves, e.g., the Ankr hack in December 2022 (Blockworks, 2022; Forbes, 2022). Therefore, it is unlikely that smart contract audits can effectively reduce the risk related to private key compromises.

2.3.2. Audit engagement and fees

Little is known about the amounts paid for audits, as protocols are not required to disclose such information and fees vary widely depending on the complexity of the protocol’s smart contracts and the reputation of the auditor. A smart contract audit from prominent U.S. and Switzerland-based firms such as TrailOfBits, ConsensysDiligence, OpenZeppelin, MixBytes, ChainSecurity (formerly PwC Switzerland), and Quantstamp can cost anywhere from US\$50,000 to US\$1 million, with fees ranging from US\$1000 to US\$5000 per person-hour. DeFi audits typically last from two weeks to three months, and are repeated as protocols are updated, new smart contracts are added, and deployments are expanded.⁶

The demand for smart contract audits has increased significantly due to the proliferation of DeFi protocols. However, most developers prefer to develop applications instead of performing complex audits; therefore, the supply of auditors remains low. As a result, the most prominent audit firms are often booked out three months or longer. In response, some less prominent audit firms have begun providing quick audits (within 48 h) at low cost. These audits are pejoratively known in the industry as “rubber stamp” audits, as they do not provide a high level of assurance but allow developers to state that their protocols have undergone an audit.

Protocols can also offer “bug bounties,” such as through platforms including Immunefi (<https://immunefi.com/>), which reward outside parties for finding critical vulnerabilities. For instance, Belt Finance paid US\$1.05 million to a coder named Alexander Schindwein, who identified a critical exploit worth US\$10 million (Cointelegraph, 2020).

2.4. Effect of DeFi audits on protocol value

Ex ante, DeFi audits can assure users of the safety of the protocol, thereby increasing the protocol’s value. First, as DeFi is a nascent field, many protocols are developed and maintained by persons or entities with little track record or reputation. Its open source nature also means that anyone can launch a new protocol by copying code from existing protocols, further lowering the entry barrier. Moreover, because the most important goal of DeFi is to allow users to engage in peer-to-peer transactions that are not subject to centralized oversight, many developers are anonymous or use pseudonyms for fear of government prosecution such as occurred with Tornado Cash (U.S. Treasury, 2022). This lack of verifiable information makes it extremely difficult to assess protocol quality (Wronka, 2023).

Second, DeFi users who lack the relevant expertise to verify the security of DeFi protocols may rely on the assurance provided by DeFi auditors. The traditional audit literature documents numerous benefits of financial statement audits, such as higher investor confidence and lower cost of capital (see DeFond and Zhang (2014) for a review of the literature). More relevant to our study, voluntary audits of financial statements by private firms improve the firms’ credit ratings and access to credit (Allee & Yohn, 2009; Lennox & Pittman, 2011; Lisowsky & Minnis, 2020; Minnis, 2011). Similarly, the literature suggests that reducing exposure to IT risks has a positive impact on firms’ value and information environments (Ashraf et al., 2020; Ashraf & Sunder, 2023; Kim et al., 2018; Li et al., 2012; Masli et al., 2010; Schoenfeld, 2022).

However, DeFi audits may not improve users’ confidence in protocols for several reasons. First, unlike traditional audits, which follow standards set by the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants or other professional organizations, DeFi audits have no uniformly accepted standards (U.S. Treasury, 2023). DeFi protocols and auditors negotiate to determine each audit’s scope, which can vary widely from one engagement to another. For example, most audits focus on smart contract code but pay little attention to protocol governance, organizational structure, and culture, all of which can affect the security of users’ deposits. Second, whereas traditional auditors tend to be heavily regulated, large firms with long track records, DeFi auditors are usually start-ups not subject to government regulation and with fewer reputational concerns. Third, DeFi audits are entirely voluntary, and therefore auditors must convince potential clients that their service is necessary, which can lead to conflicts of interest and competition to lower fees, negatively affecting service quality. Considering these factors, users may regard DeFi audits as “cheap talk” that provides no value (Carter & Jeng, 2021).

Finally, whereas traditional auditors have access to essential non-public information (e.g., transactions and internal control systems) that gives them an information advantage over outsiders, DeFi auditors have no such advantage. Due to the open source nature of the protocols, users and investors with substantial capital can conduct their own due diligence, which reduces the potential usefulness of DeFi audits. In the following sections, we empirically examine the relation between DeFi audits and protocol value.

⁶ For example, ConsensysDiligence notes that their audit of Aave in September 2020 took a total of 35 person-days, and TrailOfBits’ audit of Aave similarly took four person-weeks to complete. See <https://consensys.net/diligence/audits/2020/09/aave-protocol-v2/> and https://github.com/aave/aave-protocol/blob/master/docs/ToB_aave_protocol_final_report.pdf for details.

3. Variable measurement and sample description

3.1. Data sources and variable measurement

3.1.1. DeFi protocol value

We use two measures of protocol value. Our first measure, TVL, represents DeFi users' confidence in the security of protocols because most exploits involve hackers stealing user deposits. Using TVL is akin to how the banking literature uses the level of bank deposits to represent customers' confidence in the bank (e.g., [Chen et al. \(2022\)](#)). The second measure is the market capitalization of DeFi protocols' native tokens. These tokens serve two purposes. The first purpose is to facilitate the functions of smart contracts, e.g., acting as a bridge currency. Their second purpose is to govern the protocols, similar to the shares of a traditional firm. For example, token holders of a money market protocol can vote to determine the protocol's interest rate, while token holders of a stablecoin protocol can decide the degree of over-collateralization or thresholds to liquidate collateral ([Bhambhwani, 2022](#); [Han et al., 2023](#); [Makridis et al., 2023](#); [Tsoukalas & Falk, 2020](#)). They also receive profit distributions from the protocols, e.g., interest paid by borrowers. Prior studies argue that native token values can reflect the likelihood of project success ([Bakos & Halaburda, 2022](#); [Cong et al. 2021, 2022](#); [Gryglewicz et al., 2021](#); [Sockin & Xiong, 2023](#)). The value of blockchain projects' native tokens is also widely used by empirical studies to represent investors' valuation of these projects ([Bourveau et al., 2022](#); [Davydiuk et al., 2023](#); [Momtaz, 2020, 2021](#)). In summary, these two variables represent distinct but intertwined operationalizations of the value of DeFi protocols.

Following prior studies ([Bhambhwani, 2022](#); [Chiu et al., 2022](#); [Han et al., 2023](#)), we collect DeFi protocol data from DeFiLlama (<https://defillama.com>). We start with 323 DeFi protocols with at least US\$5 million in TVL as of November 9, 2021, our initial data collection date, on the eight most prominent blockchains for DeFi protocols, namely Avalanche, Binance Smart Chain, Ethereum, Fantom, Polygon, Solana, Terra, and Tron. We choose these blockchains as they each have a minimum of US\$5 billion in TVL across all protocols. All other blockchains have fewer than five *unique* protocols (i.e., not already operating on the aforementioned eight). After excluding seven protocols that do not have daily TVL on DeFiLlama as of our last data collection date of February 12, 2023, our final sample includes 316 protocols, accounting for, on average, 92% of the aggregate TVL on DeFiLlama over our sample period of November 3, 2018 to February 12, 2023. According to DeFiLlama, the two earliest protocols, Uniswap and MakerDAO, were launched on November 3, 2018 and February 1, 2019, respectively. We use the earliest date a protocol appears in DeFiLlama data to calculate *ProtocolMaturity*, the age of the protocol.

We collect daily data on protocol native tokens' market capitalization using CoinGecko's public API. Of the 316 protocols, CoinGecko has data for 212. The missing tokens are likely to be the result of some native tokens being traded only on DEXs and not on major centralized exchanges, thus limiting the ability of CoinGecko to collect these tokens' values.

3.1.2. DeFi audits

We collect data on the audits of the 316 protocols from a variety of sources including GitHub, protocol websites, and smart contract auditors' websites. [Table IA2](#) provides links to the websites that host the audit reports for a sample of 30 protocols.⁷ We collect the names of smart contract auditors and download the reports from these links. If we cannot find a protocol's audit information from these sources, we supplement with Google searches to verify that the protocol is not audited. We find that 88% of the protocols in our sample (i.e., 277 out of 316) are audited. It is worth noting that audits of the same protocol by different auditors may not be comparable, as some auditors are more rigorous than others. This variation may introduce noise in our measure.

We create several measures of audit characteristics for each protocol. Our first measure, *Num.Auditors*, is the number of auditors for a protocol. Using the statistics on the audited protocols and their audit reports, we create three protocol-day-level measures of audit quality. First, we use the size of auditors' audited protocols (*AuditorAvg.TVL* and *AuditorSumTVL*), because the audit literature generally concludes that Big N auditors, which audit the largest clients by total assets, have higher audit quality than other auditors ([DeFond et al., 2017](#)). *AuditorAvg.TVL* is the average TVL of all protocols audited by an auditor on a given day, aggregated across all auditors for a protocol.⁸ *AuditorSumTVL*, is the sum of TVL of all of the protocols audited by an auditor on that day, aggregated across all auditors for a protocol.⁹ Next, we use audit report length (*AuditReportLengths*) to capture auditor effort, which is conceptually similar to how the traditional audit literature uses audit hours to measure audit quality ([DeFond & Zhang, 2014](#)). *AuditReportLengths* is the sum of the length of prior audit reports for a protocol as of each date.¹⁰ Note that because there are no regulations on auditing DeFi protocols, auditors can choose what information to include in their audit reports (e.g., how much boilerplate is used in the reports), the level of detail, and the presentation format, introducing noise in this measure. We set these three audit quality variables to zero for

⁷ The list of DeFi protocols and their auditors can be downloaded at <https://www.allenhuang.org/blockchain-crypto.html>.

⁸ For example, as of December 31, 2020, the SushiSwap protocol had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield. The average TVL of all of the protocols that had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield were US\$156 million and US\$168 million as of that day, respectively. Thus, the *AuditorAvg.TVL* for SushiSwap on December 31, 2020, is $\$156 + \$168 = \$324$ million.

⁹ For example, as of December 31, 2020, SushiSwap protocol had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield. The total TVL of all of the protocols that had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield were \$939 million and \$1008 million as of that day, respectively. Thus, *AuditorSumTVL* for SushiSwap on December 31, 2020, is $\$939 + \$1008 = \$1947$ million.

¹⁰ For example, Aave was first audited by TrailOfBits with an audit report of 55 pages released on September 25, 2019, then by OpenZeppelin with an audit report of 31 pages released on January 15, 2020. *AuditReportLengths* for Aave was zero before September 25, 2019; 55 between September 25, 2019, and January 14, 2020; and 86 on and after January 15, 2020.

unaudited protocols.

We also create a parsimonious measure of audit quality using the first principal component of *AuditorAvg.TVL*, *AuditorSumTVL*, and *AuditReportLengths* and label it as *AuditQualityComposite*. We detail the calculations of these variables in the appendix.

3.1.3. DeFi exploits

We collect data on DeFi exploits from rekt (rekt.news/leaderboard) and de.fi (de.fi/rekt-database). We identify 39 code-related exploits between November 2018 and February 2023 for our sample of 316 protocols. We exclude exploits related to social engineering or private key compromises because they are usually beyond the scope of smart contract audits (see details in Section 2.3.1). We list the number of exploits by category in Table IA1. Four protocols, namely Compound, CREAM Finance, Indexed Finance, and Saddle Finance, are exploited twice during the sample period. We define *Exploits* as the number of times a protocol has been exploited, with the value set to zero for protocols not exploited.

3.1.4. Data sources of control variables

In our empirical analyses, we control for the security and technical prowess of a protocol that users can observe without audits. Because most protocols' codebases are open source and listed on GitHub, we use the number of contributors on the protocols' GitHub pages, *GitHubContributors*, as the measure. We set the value to zero for protocols without a GitHub page or if the page lists zero developers. We find that 73% of our sample protocols have GitHub depositories, with an average of 4.3 contributors. Note that Howell et al. (2019) and Bourveau et al. (2022) document that only 53% of initial coin offerings have GitHub codes. The more prevalent GitHub usage among DeFi protocols may be due to DeFi's greater reliance on open source code to build trust and attract users.

We also collect data on the daily number of tweets made by each protocol to create *CumulativeTweets*, a measure of the amount of information available to DeFi users (Ante, 2023; Shen et al., 2019). We first search for the Twitter handles for each protocol and then collect these handles' tweets using Twitter's public API. After merging DeFiLlama and Twitter data, we have tweets from 258 protocols. We set *CumulativeTweets* for the remaining 58 protocols without Twitter handles to zero.

3.2. Sample description

In Table 1, we present the summary statistics of the protocols at the protocol level using sample averages and statistics at the protocol-day level. As shown, the average protocol has 1.4 auditors. At least 25% of the protocols have two or more auditors, and 10% have three or more auditors. In an analysis reported in Appendix Table IA3, we find that the larger and more mature protocols are more likely to be audited (although both findings are only statistically significant at the 10% level). The average protocol has a sample average TVL of US\$332 million and is 269 days old. We find that the average protocol in our sample has 4.3 developers and that 10% of the protocols have 13 or more developers. The average market capitalization of the protocols in our sample is US\$197 million. The median number of tweets is 772 over our sample period, with the top 10% of the protocols posting over 3275 tweets. Most of the protocols are not exploited, as the average *Exploits* is 0.12 for the sample protocols.

At the protocol-day level, the average TVL and *ProtocolMaturity* are US\$448 million and 317 days, respectively. *AuditorAvg.TVL* is US\$290 million and *AuditorSumTVL* is US\$4.4 billion. The average audit report has 23.9 pages (untabulated) and the average number of audit report pages available for a protocol on a given day (*AuditReportLengths*) is 32.4 pages. Last, we report two date-level variables that measure aggregate user deposits in DeFi protocols (*Agg.TVL*) and aggregate market capitalization of DeFi protocols' native tokens (*Agg.TokenValue*) that have averages of US\$53 billion and US\$21 billion, respectively.

Table 2 lists all auditors whose protocol audits equal an aggregate average TVL (i.e., *SumTVL*) of at least US\$500 million. For this table, we calculate the average TVL of a protocol using the average TVL over the sample period for which data are available. We designate an auditor as prominent (*BigAuditor*) if its *SumTVL* exceeds US\$10 billion. These auditors include the largest and arguably most reputable smart contract auditors in the DeFi industry, namely TrailOfBits, Quantstamp, Peckshield, MixBytes, Certik, ChainSecurity, OpenZeppelin, and Solidified. We use this list to construct *Num.BigAuditors*. We also note that the average unaudited protocol has US\$160 million in average TVL, which is approximately 50% of the US\$332 million across all of the protocols in Table 1, consistent with the notion that audits are positively related to protocol TVL.

4. Empirical evidence on DeFi audits

4.1. Audits and DeFi value: cross-sectional analyses

To investigate the relation between DeFi audits and protocol values, we begin by estimating the following regression at the protocol level:

$$Avg.TVL/Avg.TokenValue = AuditingVariable + Controls + \gamma + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where *AuditingVariable* includes *Num.Auditors*, *Num.BigAuditors*, *AuditorSumTVL*, *AuditorAvg.TVL*, *AuditReportLengths*, and *AuditQualityComposite*. The control variables include *Avg.ProtocolMaturity*, *GitHubContributors*, and *CumulativeTweets*. We also control for the average aggregate DeFi TVL (*Avg.Agg.TVL*) in the tests of *Avg.TVL* and average aggregate DeFi token values (*Avg.Agg.TokenValue*) in the tests of *Avg.TokenValue*. All of the average variables are measured using the average of the values over the sample period for each protocol. We further include blockchain fixed effects to account for unobservable cross-sectional differences in blockchains that may

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

This table presents summary statistics of the main variables. Variable definitions are in the Appendix.

	N	Mean	SD	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90
Protocol-level Variables								
<i>Avg.TVL (millions USD)</i>	316	332.0	1020.6	3.0	8.1	32.7	158.4	637.9
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	316	1.4	1.1	0	1	1	2	3
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>	316	0.7	0.7	0	0	1	1	2
<i>Avg.Agg.TVL (millions USD)</i>	316	110,021	15,610	94,870	106,333	111,315	118,426	120,688
<i>Avg.ProtocolMaturity (days)</i>	316	269	196	32	100	250	404	511
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	316	4.3	7.3	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.0	13.0
<i>CumulativeTweets (raw)</i>	316	1352	1766	0	187	772	1824	3275
<i>Avg.TokenValue (millions USD)</i>	212	197	756	2	7	22	89	416
<i>Avg.Agg.TokenValue (millions USD)</i>	316	37,747	5021	31,426	35,584	38,393	40,635	42,810
<i>Exploits</i>	316	0.1	0.4	0	0	0	0	1
Protocol-day-level Variables								
<i>TVL (millions USD)</i>	180,623	448	1662	0.5	3	22	154	838
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	180,623	1.4	1.1	0	1	1	2	3
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>	180,623	0.7	0.8	0	0	1	1	2
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL (millions USD)</i>	180,623	290	595	0	5	107	348	724
<i>AuditorSumTVL (millions USD)</i>	180,623	4376	7136	0	8	833	6172	14,336
<i>AuditReportLengths (pages)</i>	180,623	32.4	35.5	0	9.0	23.0	42.0	72.0
<i>ProtocolMaturity (days)</i>	180,623	317	221	58	144	291	449	592
<i>CumulativeTweets (raw)</i>	180,623	930	1316	0	0	467	1266	2427
<i>TokenValue (millions USD)</i>	115,352	267	1094	1	4	21	101	494
Date-level Variables								
<i>Agg.TVL (millions USD)</i>	1562	52,665	64,924	326	533	14,305	88,846	162,872
<i>Agg.TokenValue (millions USD)</i>	1473	20,929	24,122	384	556	8123	39,744	59,036

explain DeFi protocol value.

We tabulate the results in Table 3. In columns (1)–(2) of Panel A, we find that the protocols with more auditors, especially prominent auditors, are associated with a greater amount of *TVL*. Based on the estimated coefficients, each additional auditor and prominent auditor is associated with a US\$10.4 million and US\$21.5 million increase in the average *TVL* of a protocol, respectively.¹¹ These amounts are economically significant, as the latter represents a 6.4% increase in *TVL* relative to the average *TVL* of US\$332 million. When examining whether audit quality influences *TVL*, using alternative measures of audit quality, as shown in columns (3)–(6), we find positive and statistically significant (at the 1% level) coefficients on *AuditorSumTVL*, *AuditorAvg.TVL*, and *AuditQuality-Composite*, consistent with the notion that high-quality audits or at least audits by larger auditors increase DeFi protocol users' perceived security level. We do not find significant results for *AuditReportLengths* (column (5)). The lack of relation between audit report length and *TVL* is likely due to the fact that auditors can choose what information to include in their reports, and therefore longer reports may contain more boilerplate terms or redundant information, introducing noise in this measure.

In terms of control variables, we find that a protocol's age (*Avg.ProtocolMaturity*), number of developers (*GitHubContributors*), and tweets (*CumulativeTweets*) are all positively associated with *TVL*, suggesting that protocol maturity, technical proficiency, and the amount of available information are all positively related to user deposits (Howell et al. (2019); Bourveau et al. (2022)). In Table 3, Panel B, we find similar results using *Avg.TokenValue* to measure investors' valuation of DeFi protocols. For instance, we find that each additional *Num.Auditor* is associated with a US\$8.8 million increase in token value.¹²

Next, we examine the relation between DeFi audits and protocol values using protocol-day-level data. In addition to the control variables in the protocol-level analysis, we include date fixed effects to control for time-varying macroeconomic factors and market sentiment. We cluster all standard errors at the date level (Petersen, 2009) and report the results in Table 4.

Similar to our findings at the protocol level in Table 3, we find that more auditors, more prominent auditors, and higher quality auditors are associated with a higher *TVL* (Panel A) and protocol token value (Panel B). The only exception is that the coefficient on *Num.BigAuditors* is not significant in Panel B. Interestingly, unlike in our protocol-level regressions, we find significant coefficients on *AuditReportLengths* in our protocol-day-level regressions, likely due to the increased power of the test caused by a larger sample size. In robustness tests, we find results similar to those in Tables 3 and 4 when restricting the sample to only audited protocols (untabulated). Overall, our evidence in this section suggests that users and investors perceive that auditors, especially those of higher quality, provide at least some assurance regarding the safety of their funds or tokens as investments.

¹¹ We calculate these magnitudes using $e^{17.37+0.26} - e^{17.37} = 10,383,633$, as the coefficient is 0.26 for *Num.Auditor* and the mean log value of *Avg.TVL* is 17.37. For *Num.BigAuditor*, we calculate $e^{17.37+0.48} - e^{17.37} = 21,544,097$.

¹² We calculate these magnitudes using $e^{17.04+0.30} - e^{17.04} = 8,795,707$, as the coefficient is 0.30 for *Num.Auditor* and the mean log value of *Avg.TokenValue* is 17.04.

Table 2

List of Auditors, Total Value Locked (TVL), and Token Value

This table presents the list of auditors and the TVL and token values of their audited protocols. Variable definitions are presented in the Appendix.

Auditor Name	SumTVL	Avg.TVL	SumTokenValue	Avg.TokenValue	# of Audited Protocols
TrailOfBits ^a	30,400	1790	6950	535	17
Quantstamp ^a	27,300	882	5330	213	31
Peckshield ^a	24,700	550	6000	172	45
MixBytes ^a	23,700	2370	3180	318	10
Certik ^a	22,200	265	8910	139	84
ChainSecurity ^a	20,900	2320	9280	1550	9
OpenZeppelin ^a	15,800	929	5770	444	17
Solidified ^a	11,100	1860	8170	2040	6
Coinspect	8970	2240	7500	1870	4
SigmaPrime	7510	2500	1440	479	3
RuntimeVerification	7420	1860	1100	367	4
Oxorio	6520	6520	494	494	1
StateMind	6520	6520	494	494	1
Cryptonics	4460	1110	540	135	4
SlowMist	3990	235	1560	97	17
ConsensysDiligence	3100	387	1270	317	8
Halborn	2460	205	825	91	12
Haechi	2180	272	806	101	8
Kudelski	2020	225	592	65	9
Cryptomanics	1870	1870	774	774	1
Iosiro	1530	306	1490	372	5
Bramah Systems	1130	563	450	225	2
Hacken	955	136	220	36	7
Inspx	814	271	72	36	3
Paladin	814	271	–	–	3
Vailx	804	804	72	72	1
Zokyo	745	186	674	169	4
Dave Hoover	721	721	–	–	1
Praetorian	721	721	–	–	1
Neodyme	691	230	181	60	3
LeastAuthority	606	151	805	268	4
SolidityFinance	593	74	136	22	8
Ackee	555	555	10	10	1
ABDK Consulting	533	178	94	31	3

All values except *ProtocolsAudited* are in millions USD.^a Classified as a *BigAuditor* as its *SumTVL* is greater than \$10 billion.

4.2. DeFi audits and protocol value: event study

In the above sections, we use cross-sectional analyses to document that DeFi audits are associated with protocol value. However, these results may be driven by reverse causality (e.g., more valuable protocols are able to afford auditors) or omitted correlated variables (e.g., more secure protocols are more likely to undergo voluntary audits and attract more deposits). To mitigate these endogeneity concerns, we adopt an event study research design using two events, namely the protocols' first audits and the collapse of TerraUSD stablecoin.

4.2.1. Post-first audit

In the first event study, we examine how the first audit of each protocol affects its TVL and token value. Empirically, we re-estimate the protocol-day-level regression in Table 4 using *PostAudit* as *AuditingVariable*. To ensure that we only include the relevant sample period, we also restrict the sample to audited protocols and the 60 days before and after their first audit.¹³ We further exclude the 30-day window immediately before and after the audit date, because the date on the audit report may not be the date that the report is publicly released and to account for the possibility that DeFi users and investors are not immediately aware of the audits. That is, we use days -90 to -31 as the pre-first-audit window (*PostAudit* equals zero) and days $+31$ to $+90$ as the post-first-audit window (*PostAudit* equals one).

The results in Table 5 show positive and significant coefficients on *PostAudit* in column (1) of Panel A and Panel B. These findings are consistent with the notion that DeFi protocols experience an increase in both TVL and native token value after their first audits, corroborating the positive association we document in the cross-sectional analyses. In terms of economic magnitude, we find that the protocols exhibit an increase in their TVL of US\$34.7 million after a first audit, representing a 14% increase over the mean TVL of US\$248 million.¹⁴

¹³ Our findings are similar when using 30-day, 90-day, and 120-day windows (untabulated).

¹⁴ We calculate these magnitudes using $e^{17.41+0.67} - e^{17.41} = 34,731,483$, as the coefficient is 0.67 for *PostAudit* and the mean log value of TVL is 17.41 for the sample in column (1) of Panel A of Table 5.

Table 3

DeFi Audits and Protocol Value: A Protocol-level Analysis

This table presents regressions of a protocol's average total value locked (*Avg.TVL*) on auditing-related variables in Panel A and a protocol's average native token market capitalization (*Avg.TokenValue*) on auditing-related variables in Panel B. All variables except *Num.Auditors*, *Num.BigAuditors* and *GitHubContributors* are natural logged. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively. Variable definitions are presented in the Appendix.

Panel A: TVL	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Dependent Variable	<i>Avg.TVL</i>					
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	0.26** (0.12)					
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>		0.48*** (0.18)				
<i>AuditorSumTVL</i>			0.20*** (0.05)			
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL</i>				0.10*** (0.04)		
<i>AuditReportLengths</i>					0.02 (0.09)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>						0.22*** (0.08)
<i>Avg.ProtocolMaturity</i>	1.76*** (0.34)	1.77*** (0.34)	1.65*** (0.34)	1.78*** (0.34)	1.93*** (0.34)	1.74*** (0.34)
<i>Avg.Agg.TVL</i>	0.28 (0.79)	0.36 (0.79)	0.12 (0.77)	0.11 (0.78)	0.05 (0.79)	0.14 (0.78)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.05*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.05*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)	0.06*** (0.02)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.09** (0.05)	0.10** (0.05)	0.07 (0.05)	0.08* (0.05)	0.09** (0.05)	0.08* (0.05)
Fixed Effects	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain
R ²	.23	.23	.25	.23	.22	.23
Observations	316	316	316	316	316	316
Panel B: Token Value	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Dependent Variable	<i>Avg.TokenValue</i>					
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	0.30** (0.12)					
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>		0.56*** (0.19)				
<i>AuditorSumTVL</i>			0.18*** (0.06)			
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL</i>				0.10** (0.04)		
<i>AuditReportLengths</i>					0.12 (0.10)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>						0.24** (0.09)
<i>Avg.ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.85** (0.38)	0.88** (0.37)	0.91** (0.37)	1.01*** (0.37)	1.05*** (0.38)	0.96** (0.37)
<i>Avg.Agg.TokenValue</i>	-0.55 (0.85)	-0.53 (0.84)	-0.71 (0.84)	-0.69 (0.84)	-0.72 (0.86)	-0.68 (0.84)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.07*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)	0.08*** (0.02)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.06 (0.07)	0.06 (0.07)	0.06 (0.07)	0.07 (0.07)	0.07 (0.07)	0.06 (0.07)
Fixed Effects	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain
R ²	.26	.27	.27	.26	.24	.26
Observations	212	212	212	212	212	212

Next, we examine whether the relation is affected by the quality of the first audit by including the interaction between *PostAudit* and *AuditQualityComposite*. We find that the coefficient on *PostAudit* × *AuditQualityComposite* is positive and significant, as shown in column (2) of both panels. These results are consistent with the takeaway in Tables 3 and 4 that higher quality audits can further enhance the confidence of users and investors in DeFi protocols and strengthen the effect of DeFi audits on protocol value.

4.2.2. TerraUSD stablecoin collapse

While our results in the first-audit event study provide more causal evidence of the effect of audit on protocol value, whether and when to obtain a first audit remains a protocol's decision. To further alleviate endogeneity concerns, we use an event that is arguably exogenous to our sample protocols, namely the TerraUSD (UST) stablecoin collapse.

Table 4

DeFi Audits and Protocol Value: A Protocol-Day-level Analysis

This table presents regressions of a protocol's daily total value locked (TVL) on auditing-related variables in Panel A and a protocol's daily native token market capitalization (*TokenValue*) on auditing-related variables in Panel B. Standard errors are clustered at the date-level and are reported in parentheses below the coefficients. All variables except *Num.Auditors*, *Num.BigAuditors* and *GitHubContributors* are natural logged. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively. Variable definitions are presented in the Appendix.

Panel A: TVL	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	TVL					
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	0.46*** (0.01)					
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>		0.14*** (0.01)				
<i>AuditorSumTVL</i>			0.29*** (0.00)			
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL</i>				0.16*** (0.00)		
<i>AuditReportLengths</i>					0.06*** (0.00)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>						0.36*** (0.00)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.90*** (0.02)	1.00*** (0.02)	0.90*** (0.02)	0.94*** (0.02)	1.00*** (0.02)	0.93*** (0.02)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.02*** (0.00)	0.04*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)	0.04*** (0.00)	0.03*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.11*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)	0.11*** (0.00)
Fixed Effects	Chain, Date					
R ²	.29	.27	.31	.29	.27	.29
Observations	180,623	180,623	180,623	180,623	180,623	180,623
Panel B: Token Value	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>TokenValue</i>					
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	0.35*** (0.00)					
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>		0.00 (0.01)				
<i>AuditorSumTVL</i>			0.21*** (0.00)			
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL</i>				0.13*** (0.00)		
<i>AuditReportLengths</i>					0.12*** (0.00)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>						0.30*** (0.00)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.60*** (0.01)	0.73*** (0.01)	0.64*** (0.01)	0.67*** (0.01)	0.72*** (0.01)	0.66*** (0.01)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.07*** (0.00)	0.08*** (0.00)	0.07*** (0.00)	0.08*** (0.00)	0.08*** (0.00)	0.08*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.12*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)	0.12*** (0.00)	0.12*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)	0.12*** (0.00)
Fixed Effects	Chain, Date					
R ²	.37	.36	.40	.39	.37	.39
Observations	115,352	115,352	115,352	115,352	115,352	115,352

Terra-LUNA is a blockchain that, combined with the Anchor DeFi protocol, relied on algorithmic issuance instead of collateral to maintain its UST stablecoin peg to the U.S. dollar (Briola et al., 2023). Its rapid de-pegging in May 2022 wiped out hundreds of billions of cryptocurrency value. The aggregate TVL across all of the protocols tracked by DeFiLlama dropped from US\$185 billion on May 6, 2022 to US\$107 billion on May 14, 2022, and to US\$66 billion on June 19, 2022. We use the TerraUSD collapse as an exogenous shock to the confidence of users and investors in DeFi protocols. We posit that DeFi audits, which should identify vulnerabilities in the protocols and provide assurance as to their security, can lessen the negative impact of the shock. That is, we expect audited protocols to suffer a milder drop in TVL and native token value than unaudited protocols in response to the shock.¹⁵

¹⁵ Another important event for the cryptocurrency market was the collapse of the FTX exchange in November 2022. We do not use this event because it was a failure of a centralized exchange.

Table 5**DeFi Audits and Protocol Value: An Event Study around First Audits**

This table presents the results of an event study of how protocols' first audit affects their total value locked (TVL) and native tokens' market capitalization (*TokenValue*) in Panels A and B respectively. The sample includes audited protocols and days -90 to -31 as the pre-first-audit window (*PostAudit* equals zero) and days $+31$ to $+90$ as the post-first-audit window (*PostAudit* equals one). Standard errors are clustered at the date-level and reported in parentheses below the coefficients. All variables except *PostAudit* and *GitHubContributors* are natural logged. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively. Variable definitions are presented in the Appendix.

Panel A: TVL	(1)	(2)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	TVL	
<i>PostAudit</i>	0.67*** (0.06)	0.51*** (0.07)
<i>PostAudit</i> × <i>AuditQualityComposite</i>		0.32*** (0.05)
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>		0.17*** (0.04)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.36*** (0.02)	0.33*** (0.02)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.06*** (0.00)	0.07*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.09*** (0.01)	0.08*** (0.01)
Fixed Effects	Chain, Date	Chain, Date
R ²	.22	.25
Observations	11,638	11,638
Panel B: Token Value	(1)	(2)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>TokenValue</i>	
<i>PostAudit</i>	0.13*** (0.03)	-0.12*** (0.05)
<i>PostAudit</i> × <i>AuditQualityComposite</i>		0.31*** (0.03)
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>		-0.13*** (0.03)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.31*** (0.02)	0.30*** (0.02)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.08*** (0.00)	0.08*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.03*** (0.01)	0.05*** (0.01)
Fixed Effects	Chain, Date	Chain, Date
R ²	.39	.40
Observations	6089	6089

Empirically, we use May 11, 2022 as the event date because it is the date that the Terra-LUNA blockchain shut down.¹⁶ We estimate protocol-day-level regressions using all of the protocols and the 120-day window centered on the event date, i.e., 60 days before and 60 days after. We do not exclude the 30 days around the event date, because the Terra-LUNA collapse is highly salient and, therefore, DeFi users and investors should be aware of the event immediately. We use the model in Table 5, replacing *PostAudit* with *PostLUNA*. We report the results of our analysis in Panels A and B of Table 6 for TVL and *TokenValue*, respectively.

As shown in column (1) of both Panels A and B, we observe a negative and statistically significant coefficient on *PostLUNA* for TVL and *TokenValue*, respectively, which is consistent with observations in the market regarding the significant drop in TVL and cryptocurrency values. More importantly, when examining the coefficients on *PostLUNA* × *Num.Auditors* and *PostLUNA* × *AuditQualityComposite* in columns (2) and (3) of Panels A and B, respectively, of Table 6, we document positive and statistically significant coefficients. These findings suggest that the post-LUNA drop in TVL was relatively muted for protocols with more auditors and higher quality auditors. In terms of economic magnitude, each additional auditor is associated with a US\$1.3 million *smaller* reduction in TVL post-LUNA.¹⁷ In summary, both event studies provide strong evidence that DeFi audits indeed enhance protocol value, corroborating the evidence from the cross-sectional analyses in the previous section.

¹⁶ We find similar results using May 7, 2022, the day that TerraUSD (UST) stablecoin began to de-peg, as the event date (untabulated).

¹⁷ We calculate these magnitudes using $e^{16.53+0.08} - e^{16.53} = 1, 257, 376$, as the coefficient is 0.08 for *PostAudit* × *Num.Auditors* and the mean log value of TVL is 16.53 for the sample in column (2).

Table 6

DeFi Audits and Protocol Value: An Event Study around the TerraUSD Collapse

This table presents the results of an event study on how the TerraUSD collapse affects protocol's total value locked (*TVL*) and native tokens' market capitalization (*TokenValue*) in Panels A and B respectively. We use all protocols and the 120-day window centered on the event date. Standard errors are clustered at the date-level and are reported in parentheses below the coefficients. All variables except *GitHubContributors* and *NumAuditors* are natural logged. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively. Variable definitions are presented in the Appendix.

Panel A: TVL	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>TVL</i>		
<i>PostLUNA</i>	-1.50*** (0.06)		
<i>PostLUNA</i> × <i>Num.Auditors</i>		0.08*** (0.01)	
<i>PostLUNA</i> × <i>AuditQualityComposite</i>			0.05*** (0.01)
<i>Num.Auditors</i>		0.31*** (0.01)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>			0.30*** (0.00)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	2.02*** (0.04)	1.99*** (0.04)	2.00*** (0.04)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.02*** (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)	0.02*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.14*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)	0.12*** (0.00)
Fixed Effects	Chain	Chain, Date	Chain, Date
R ²	.23	.25	.26
Observations	36,903	36,903	36,903
Panel B: Token Value	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>TokenValue</i>		
<i>PostLUNA</i>	-1.11*** (0.04)		
<i>PostLUNA</i> × <i>Num.Auditors</i>		0.09*** (0.01)	
<i>PostLUNA</i> × <i>AuditQualityComposite</i>			0.12*** (0.01)
<i>Num.Auditors</i>		0.30*** (0.01)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>			0.25*** (0.01)
<i>ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.98*** (0.02)	0.86*** (0.02)	0.95*** (0.02)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.10*** (0.00)	0.09*** (0.00)	0.09*** (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	0.15*** (0.00)	0.14*** (0.00)	0.13*** (0.00)
Fixed Effects	Chain	Chain, Date	Chain, Date
R ²	.25	.28	.31
Observations	24,272	24,272	24,272

4.3. DeFi audits and protocol exploits

The above results are consistent with the notion that DeFi audits, especially those conducted by higher quality auditors, provide assurance to users and improve protocol value. In this section, we explore whether investors' confidence in DeFi audits is justified, by examining the relation between DeFi audits and protocol exploits. Specifically, we estimate the following regression at the protocol level:

$$\text{Exploits} = \text{AuditingVariables} + \text{Controls} + \gamma + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where the dependent variable is *Exploits*. We include the control variables in Table 3 such as *Avg.ProtocolMaturity*, *GitHubContributors*, *CumulativeTweets*, and the average aggregate DeFi TVL (*Avg.Agg.TVL*). We further control for protocol size (*Avg.TVL*) because larger protocols are more likely to attract hackers. All of the regressions include blockchain fixed effects.

We tabulate the results in Table 7. Interestingly, we do not find a significant relation between DeFi protocols' audits and their likelihood of being exploited. While it is possible that DeFi audits are not effective in reducing exploit risks, this nonsignificant result may also be due to a lack of power from the small sample size or sample selection bias. For example, because exploits are usually

Table 7

DeFi Audits and Protocol Exploits

This table presents the relation between the likelihood of a protocol exploit and auditing-related variables. All variables except *Exploits*, *Num.Auditors*, *Num.BigAuditors* and *GitHubContributors* are natural logged. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively. Variable definitions are in the Appendix.

<i>Dependent Variable</i>	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>Exploits</i>						
<i>Num.Auditors</i>	0.03 (0.02)					
<i>Num.BigAuditors</i>		0.05 (0.03)				
<i>AuditorSumTVL</i>			0.01 (0.01)			
<i>AuditorAvg.TVL</i>				0.00 (0.01)		
<i>AuditReportLengths</i>					0.01 (0.02)	
<i>AuditQualityComposite</i>						0.01 (0.02)
<i>Avg.TVL</i>	0.02** (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)	0.02** (0.01)
<i>Avg.ProtocolMaturity</i>	0.11* (0.07)	0.12* (0.07)	0.12* (0.07)	0.12* (0.07)	0.12* (0.07)	0.12* (0.07)
<i>Avg.Agg.TVL</i>	-0.23 (0.15)	-0.22 (0.15)	-0.26* (0.15)	-0.26* (0.15)	-0.25* (0.15)	-0.25* (0.15)
<i>GitHubContributors</i>	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)
<i>CumulativeTweets</i>	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.01)
Fixed Effects	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain	Chain
R ²	.09	.09	.08	.08	.08	.08
Observations	316	316	316	316	316	316

uncovered by developers, users, auditors, or other stakeholders, unaudited protocols may underreport their exploits, similar to how companies underreport cybersecurity incidents (Amir et al., 2018). In addition, protocols that are more complicated and thus are more likely to have loopholes may be more likely to hire auditors. These sample selection issues can bias toward finding a nonsignificant relation between DeFi audits and protocol exploits. In terms of control variables, we find that the protocols with higher TVL are more likely to be exploited, consistent with the intuition that these protocols offer higher rewards and thus are more attractive targets.

4.4. Implications of our findings

From the perspective of DeFi investors, our findings that protocol audits are associated with greater deposits (i.e., larger TVL) and higher market capitalization provide empirical evidence that users and investors perceive that smart contract audits provide at least some assurance regarding the safety of their deposits and investments. More auditors and higher quality auditors may serve to assuage investors' concerns regarding the risks of coding errors and other exploits. As such, our results shed additional light on the determinants of token prices (Biais et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021; Makarov & Schoar, 2020).

Our findings also have implications for protocol developers, in that they may leverage audits to attract users and deposits to enhance the value of protocols' tokens. While the results are preliminary, their economic magnitudes are consistent with DeFi audits being worthy investments, supplementing recent studies on factors that contribute to the success of blockchain projects (Bourveau et al., 2022; Fisch & Momtaz, 2020; Howell et al., 2020; Lyandres et al., 2022).

From a regulatory perspective, the decision to conduct an audit is generally made by insiders such as developers and early investors. Although these decisions often must be approved by protocols' native token holders through on-chain votes, in reality, insiders control most of the voting tokens (Bhambhvani, 2022; Davydiuk et al., 2023; Han et al., 2023; Makridis et al., 2023; Tsoukalas & Falk, 2020). For example, when the DeFi protocol Compound selected OpenZeppelin as its auditor, the vote tally was 1.37 million FOR and only 3000 AGAINST. Of the 1.37 million FOR votes, a16z (321,000), Polychain Capital (306,000), Bain Capital Ventures (323,000), and CTO and Compound co-founder, Geoffrey Hayes (101,000), accounted for the majority.¹⁸ Our interviews with DeFi protocol developers also suggest that venture capitalists, who are early investors of projects, often have strong preferences for certain auditors. In essence, our evidence supports the SEC's claim that DeFi tokens are securities because their value is ultimately tied to the efforts of insiders, one of the criteria for determining what a security is (SEC v. W.J. Howey Co., 328 U.S. 293 [1946]).

As an early entry into research on this nascent industry, our paper is not without limitations. For example, while our measures of

¹⁸ See <https://compound.finance/governance/proposals/76> for a detailed breakdown of the votes.

DeFi audit quality (i.e., the TVL of protocols audited by auditors and audit report length) are similar to those used in the traditional audit literature (i.e., auditor size and hours), these measures contain noise. In addition, they may capture auditor reputation and perceived audit quality rather than actual quality (DeFond & Zhang, 2014). Indeed, we do not find a significant relation between our measures of audit quality and the likelihood of protocol exploits. Furthermore, our empirical analyses using a cross-sectional design and our two event studies are subject to endogeneity concerns.

Our paper brings to light the heterogeneity of DeFi audits. For example, many protocols have multiple auditors, which raises questions regarding whether audits by different auditors exhibit redundancy or, alternatively, broaden the audit's scope. The literature on joint audits finds inconclusive evidence on how they affect audit quality. For example, while Zerni et al. (2012) find joint audits to be associated with higher audit quality, André et al. (2016) and Lesage et al. (2017) fail to document a significant relation. Deng et al. (2014) and Lobo et al. (2017) further suggest that joint audits can lower audit quality due to internal opinion shopping and free riding. DeFi audits may be an ideal setting to answer this question, because such audit reports often discuss the scope of the audits. We consider these questions to be a fruitful area for future research.

5. Conclusion

The DeFi industry has the potential to upend traditional finance institutions due to its lower costs, greater transparency of transactions, and higher efficiency (Harvey et al., 2021). DeFi protocols run completely on smart contracts that can perform the functions of exchanges, banks, brokerages, and investment platforms. However, the code that powers these protocols may not be comprehensible by the average user, nor do the protocols have a significant track record, given that the DeFi industry is in its infancy. One way to bridge such information asymmetry is for users and protocols to engage smart contract auditors to check and verify the code.

In this study, we provide an overview of the DeFi audit industry and an empirical analysis of the relation between DeFi audits and protocol value. We find that protocols with more auditors and those with higher quality auditors have higher TVL and DeFi token value. Using an event study approach, we document that protocols exhibit a significant increase in TVL and token value after their first audits, especially those conducted by more auditors and by higher quality auditors. Using the collapse of the TerraUSD stablecoin, which damaged user and investor confidence in the DeFi industry and reduced the aggregate DeFi TVL by almost 65%, as a shock, we find that protocols with more auditors or higher quality auditors exhibit a milder drop in TVL and token value. In essence, our evidence suggests that DeFi audits, especially those conducted by prominent auditors, enhance protocol value by providing assurance regarding the safety of users' funds. Overall, our paper sheds light on DeFi audits and improves understanding of this nascent industry.

Data availability

All data are publicly available from the sources cited in the text.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2023.101270>.

Appendix: Variable definitions

Variable	Definition
Outcome Variables	
TVL_{it}	Total value locked (i.e., deposited) on protocol i on date t . Source: defillama.com.
$Avg.TVL_i$	Average of total value locked on protocol i over its sample period. Protocols' sample periods differ due to different launch dates.
$TokenValue_{it}$	Market capitalization for protocol i 's native token on date t . Source: coingecko.com .
$Avg.TokenValue_i$	Average market capitalization of protocol i 's native token over its sample period. Protocols' sample periods differ due to different token launch dates.
$Exploits_i$	The total number of exploits protocol i has experienced in the sample period. Source: rekt.news and defi.yield.
Audit Quality Variables	
$Num.Auditors_{i/t}$	$Num.Auditors_{i/t}$ is the cumulative number of auditors for protocol i as of date t . $Num.Auditors_i$ is the total number of auditors for protocol i during its sample period.
$Num.BigAuditors_{i/t}$	$Num.BigAuditors_{i/t}$ is the cumulative number of auditors for protocol i as of date t . $Num.BigAuditors_i$ is the total number of auditors for protocol i during its sample period. Big auditors include TrailOfBits, Quantstamp, Peckshield, MixBytes, Certik, ChainSecurity, OpenZeppelin, and Solidified.
$AuditorAvg.TVL_{it}$	The sum of average TVL of protocols audited by protocol i 's auditors on date t . For example, as of December 31, 2020, the SushiSwap protocol had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield. The average TVL of all of the protocols that had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield were US\$156 million and US\$168 million as of that day, respectively. Thus, the $AuditorAvg.TVL$ for SushiSwap on December 31, 2020, is $156 + 168 = 324$ million.
$AuditorSumTVL_{it}$	The sum of total TVL audited by protocol i 's auditors on date t . For example, as of December 31, 2020, SushiSwap protocol had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield. The total TVL of all of the protocols that had been audited by Quantstamp and Peckshield were

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Variable	Definition
	\$939 million and \$1008 million as of that day, respectively. Thus, $AuditorSum.TVL$ for SushiSwap on December 31, 2020 is $US\$939 + US\$1008 = US\$1947$ million.
$AuditReportLengths_{it}$	The total number of pages of audit reports for protocol i as of date t . For example, Aave was first audited by TrailOfBits with an audit report of 55 pages released on September 25, 2019, then by OpenZeppelin with an audit report of 31 pages released on January 15, 2020. $AuditReportLength$ for Aave was zero before September 25, 2019; 55 between September 25, 2019 and January 14, 2020; and 86 on and after January 15, 2020.
$AuditQualityComposite_{it}$	The first principal component of $AuditorAvg.TVL_{it}$, $AuditorSumTVL_{it}$ and $AuditReportLengths_{it}$, which equals $0.62 * AuditorAvg.TVL_{it} + 0.63 * AuditorSumTVL_{it} + 0.47 * AuditReportLengths_{it}$.
$PostAudit_{it}$	An indicator variable that equals one for protocol i if day t is after the protocol's first audit date, and zero otherwise.
Other Variables	
$Agg.TVL_t$	The sum of total value locked across all protocols on date t .
$Avg.Agg.TVL_i$	Average of daily-level sum of total value locked across all protocols over the sample period of protocol i .
$Agg.TokenValue_t$	Sum of the market capitalization of all protocols' native tokens on date t .
$Avg.Agg.TokenValue_i$	Average of daily-level sum of market capitalization of all protocols' native tokens over the sample period of protocol i .
$ProtocolMaturity_{it}$	The number of days protocol i has been in operation as of date t .
$Avg.ProtocolMaturity_i$	The average number of days protocol i has been in operation in its sample period.
$GitHubContributors_i$	The total number of contributors for protocol i on github.com . We set the value to zero for protocols without a GitHub page.
$CumulativeTweets_{it}$	$CumulativeTweets_{it}$ is the cumulative number of tweets for protocol i as of date t . $CumulativeTweets_i$ is the total number of tweets for protocol i during its sample period.
$PostLUNA_t$	An indicator variable if day t after May 11, 2022, and zero otherwise.

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